

THE ECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PIKEPEARCH (SANDER LUCIPERCA) IN THE EAST ARNASOY WATER BASIN

Dekhqonova Dilorakhon Rasuljon kizi

Toshkent state agrarian university

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Abstract. *The article presents information about the characteristics of growth, fertility and reproduction of white shale (Sander lucioperca (Linnaeus, 1758) in the East Arnasoï reservoir. The data on the relationship between the body weight of pikeperch and the fecundity of Lake Tuzkan and the Talimarzhan Reservoir were compared.*

Keywords: *fecundity, IMS, INS, egg diameter, growth, reproduction, length, weight, age, gonadal weight.*

Introduction

Increasing the volume of pikeperch in natural reservoirs of our republic, as well as studying the ichthyofauna of natural reservoirs, is one of the urgent problems in the field of fisheries. Due to the attention paid to fisheries in recent years, several research works have been conducted. Studying the ichthyofauna of natural water bodies, studying the status of existing species, preventing the decrease in the number of fish species, and the ecology of valuable fish require a deeper and more complete study. *Sander lucioperca L.* is one of the most valuable commercial fish. In foreign countries, pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca L.*) has an acceptable growth rate for market size under intensive conditions. Also, pikeperch is a valuable recreational fish species [1].

The pikeperch has ecologically very plastic characteristics and can quickly adapt to the conditions of this place [2]. A large, fast-growing fish, it can reach 1 m in length and weigh 15 kg or more. Lives in the open part of rivers, lakes and reservoirs. There are semi-transient and persistent forms. Very demanding on dissolved oxygen in water. He lived in the lower reaches of the Aral Sea, Amudarya and Syrdarya Rivers. In 1963, it was brought from the Ural River to the water basins of Syrdarya and Amudarya Rivers, as well as Zarafshan River and Kashkadarya. Currently, it is distributed in all plain water bodies. White sla fish [4] it is a valuable hunting object. In the 1990s, it made up 20-25% of the fish caught in Uzbekistan and took the second-third place. It is used in fisheries to reduce the number of fish in artificial ponds.[4] therefore, it is very important to study the biology and ecology of pikeperch in the Aydar-Arnasoï lake system, especially the characteristics of reproduction.

Material methodology

On the basis of the materials obtained as a result of our scientific research hunts in the Eastern Arnasoï reservoirs in 2020-2022, the reproductive characteristics of female pikeperch caught directly from the Eastern Arnasoï reservoirs of AAKT were analyzed. It was found that pikeperch reach sexual maturity in reservoirs from the age of 2 years. According to the literature, white sla fish reach sexual maturity in 2-4 years of life in different reservoirs when they reach different lengths from 29-31 to 38-40 cm. Spawning occurs in March-April when the water temperature reaches 8-17°C. It builds a simple nest in the form of a pit or lays its eggs in the roots

of reeds and other plants at a depth of 0.5-1.5 m. Caviar sticks to sticky plants. The man guards them. Density is 80-8000 pieces. The diameter of the caviar is 0.7-1 mm.[4] Another characteristic feature of the pikeperch in the southern water basins of Uzbekistan is its rapid growth compared to the pikeperch in the northern latitudes. In our southern reservoirs, a 2-year-old pikeperch reaches sexual maturity when its body is 30-35 cm. [2]

In our research, the length of the body of two young female pikeperch in the reservoirs reached 34-36 (average 35) cm. The body length of 2-year-old female fish reached 34-46 (average 40) cm in February-March, and all of them were in the IV stage of sexual maturity. In the Eastern Arnasoi reservoir, it was found that white sla fish spawn in early February. Samples of sexual products were taken for research. Collection, processing and analysis of materials were carried out according to generally accepted ichthyological methods (Pravdin, 1966; Spanovskaya, 1976). [3] Determination of the richness of fish roe was carried out using the usual weight-measurement method. In this case, spawners were weighed as a whole, and then the amount of caviar in 1 g of sample was calculated and multiplied by the total mass of spawners to determine the individual absolute fertility (IMS thousand caviar). From each sample of caviar, 100 pieces of caviar were drawn using Mikrofod PO-5 equipment, and their dimensions were determined in mm (Dryagin 1949) [5].

Results and their discussion

In the course of our research, we analyzed the reproduction characteristics of female pikeperch in the Eastern Arnasoi reservoirs, the obtained data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Reproductive indicators of female white sla fish in water reservoirs of Uzbekistan

INDICATORS	Eastern Arnasoi n=32	Tuzkan n=30	Talimarjon n=66 (U.Mirzayev's data 1994)
Length, l (cm)	<u>34-78,8</u> 56,4	<u>36-78</u> 57,1	<u>35,5-59,4</u> 44,5
Weight, w (g)	<u>300-6600</u> 2921	<u>290-6500</u> 2539	<u>454-2914</u> 1168
Weight of gonads, q (g)	<u>50-350</u> 200	<u>48-308</u> 178	<u>39-350</u> 118
IAP (thousand pieces, caviar)	<u>56,8-4646,4</u> 214,8	<u>50,4-1205,2</u> 627,8	<u>50,1-394,1</u> 142,9
IOP (caviar/g)	<u>45,9-240,3</u> 99	<u>50,8-253</u> 123	<u>91,3-199</u> 142,2
Caviar diameter (mm)	<u>1,12-0,69</u> 0,9	<u>0,62-1,09</u> 0,88	<u>0,73-1,02</u> 0,89

The data in the table show that the pikeperch living in the Eastern Arnasoy reservoirs are larger than the pikeperch living in the Tuzkan lake and the Talimarjan reservoir (U.Mirzayev 1994). Also, the gonad weight and individual absolute fertility indicators of pikeperch found in the

Eastern Arnasoy are relatively high. It was found that the minimum, maximum and average sizes of the diameter of the sexed pikeperch caviar in the Eastern Arnasoy reservoirs are slightly higher than the size of the caviar of the pikeperch in the Tuzkan and Talimarjon reservoirs (U.Mirzayev 1994). Also, if we analyze the scientific studies conducted on the reproduction of white sla fish, according to the literature data on reproductive characteristics (in the researches of U. Mirzayev), among others, white sla fish of Talimarjon Reservoir in 1966-1969, it was determined that the individual fertility of 33.5-59.4 cm reaching sexual maturity was 50.1-394 thousand pieces [2]. When we compared these data with our results, it was found that they are close to the indicators of white sla fish in Tuzkan and Eastern Arnasoi in the AAKT. (Table 1)

We present the following information on the size of adult caviar, that is, caviar that will participate in reproduction this year. (Table 2).

Table 2

Diameter indicators of fish roe studied in the Eastern Arnasoy (optional 100 drawings, Dryagin method)																
№	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
max	1,1 2	1,1 2	1,0 3	1,0 6	1,1 2	1,1 2	1,0 3	1,0 9	1,1 2	1 1	1,0 3	1,1 2	1,1 2	1,1 2	1 1	1,1 2
min	0,6 8	0,8 1	0,7 8	0,6 8	0,7 5	0,7 8	0,7 5	0,7 1	0,7 5	0,6 8	0,6 8	0,7 5	0,6 2	0,6 2	0,7 1	0,6 8
mediu m	1,4 6	0,9 7	0,8 9	0,8 8	0,9 6	0,9 6	0,8 5	0,8 4	0,9 6	0,8 5	0,8 9	0,9 1	0,8 7	0,8 7	0,8 2	0,9 4

№	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	
ax	,09	,9 3	,9 3	,9 3	,9 3		,9 7			,9 3		,9 3	,9 7		,93	,93	,12
in	,68	,6 2	,6 2	,7 8	,7 5	,7 8	,7 5	,6 8	,7 5	,7 8	,7 8	,7 5	,7 8	,7 8	,75	,75	.68
ediu m	,92	,8 5	,8 5	,8 4	,8 2	,9 0	,8 6	,8 7	,8 6	,8 7	,8 9	,8 6	,8 7	,8 6	,84	,85	.9

In the course of research, it was found that the average indicator of female pikeperch caviar in the Eastern Arnasoi reservoirs is 0.9 +. This indicator shows that it is higher than the diameter indicators of white sla fish roe in Tuzkon and Talimarjon reservoirs (Mirzayev U. 1994). (Table 1)

As a result of the conducted research, it was found that there is an average correlation ($r = 0,7504$ va $y = 931,8x^{-0,457}$) between fish weight and INS (IOP) indicator (Fig. 1).

Figure 1.

Correlation between body weight and INS indicators of pikeperch in the Eastern Arnasoy reservoir (correlation is significant at $P < 0.01$ level).

Summary. According to the results of our scientific research, it was observed that the pikeperch reaches sexual maturity at the age of 2-3 years when the body length is 34.0-36.0 cm and the body weight is 300-400 g. body length and weight, gonad weight and individual absolute fertility indicators, as well as the diameter of caviar, are slightly higher than pikeperch found in Lake Tuzkan and Talimarjan reservoir (Mirzayev U 1994). Also, it was found that there is an average correlation ($r = 0.7504$ and $y = 931.8x-0.457$) between the weight of pikeperch and the INS (IOP) indicator studied in the East Arnasoy water basin.

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